

1 **Induction of platelet- and coagulation-related factors associated wit administration of CDK4/6**
2 **inhibitors.**

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7 We recently described therapeutic potential of CDK4/6 inhibitors in human breast cancer and
8 human lung cancer (non-small cell type) in primary chemoprophylaxis and management of (central
9 nervous system) CNS disease (1-5). Cancer is associated with an increased risk of clotting-related events
10 known as cancer-associated thrombosis (CAT) (6); endocrine therapy (tamoxifen) in human breast cancer
11 has also been associated with increased risk of thrombosis (7). Increased venous thromboembolism
12 (VTE) including deep vein thrombosis (DVT) was described in breast cancer patients treated with CDK4/6
13 inhibitors (8). Here, we evaluated transcriptional changes in platelet- and coagulation-related factors in
14 human cells following administration of CDK4/6 inhibitors, and in human tissues deficient or sufficient in
15 *Rb1*. The data appear to suggest an intrinsic link between Rb-dependent tumor suppression and the
16 clotting cascade.
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Results

Notes

Luminal A and Luminal B subtype breast cancer patients are considered HR+, or hormone receptor-positive. HR+ patients are treated with endocrine therapy - estrogen deprivation therapy; latest treatment protocols include the use of CDK4/6 inhibitors including palbociclib, ribociclib and abemaciclib in HR+ patients.

CDK4/6 inhibitors, at least as viewed through short term *in vitro* treatment, have attractive transcriptional effects which allude to positive therapeutic results (down-regulation of nucleotide synthesis molecules like TYMS and RRM2; repression of Topoisomerase IIA [TOP2A]). The risks associated with use of any drug must be weighed against its benefit. Information on long-term primary tumor evolution (as compared to transcriptional changes observed following 72 hours of *in vitro* treatment of cultured cells) following treatment of HR+ patients with endocrine therapy only versus endocrine therapy plus CDK4/6 inhibitors is limited.

We were interested to determine whether suggested DVT risk derived from CDK4/6 treatment is dependent or independent of Rb, the major cellular target of CDK4/6 relevant to therapeutic targeting in human breast cancer.

We evaluated induction of platelet- and coagulation-related factors in Jurkat cells following 72 hours of *in vitro* treatment with CDK4/6 inhibitor palbociclib, or in Jurkat cells that had been engineered to lack Rb expression (Rb -/- Jurkat) by measuring total transcription using RNA-sequencing.

Results

I. GSE182659

n=3 Jurkat DMSO 72 hours

n=3 Jurkat palbociclib 72 hours

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
2161	8.89e-10	0.2546	-6.12823	-1.560395	87.26	F12	1148/12861 =	<u>91.1</u>
5051	6.46e-18	0.2	-8.624088	-1.724845	169.54	PAFAH2	493/12861 =	<u>96.2</u>
7059	5.71e-05	0.3973	-4.024515	-1.59905	29.11	THBS3	2683/12861 =	<u>79.1</u>
56034	6.24e-22	0.1368	-9.625462	-1.316993	382.05	PDGFC	367/12681 =	<u>97.1</u>

II. GSE182659

n=3 Jurkat Rb-/- DMSO 72 hours

n=3 Jurkat Rb-/- palbociclib 72 hours

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
2161	1.64e-05	0.405	-4.3086094	-1.7459871	49.07	F12	230/12300 =	<u>98.1</u>
5051	2.13e-02	0.487	-2.3033625	-1.1207587	99.5	PAFAH2	1786/12300 =	<u>85.5</u>
7059	6.46e-03	0.583	-2.7233993	-1.5885852	21.6	THBS3	1143/12300 =	<u>90.7</u>
56034	3.05e-04	0.548	-3.6108471	-1.9793981	187.07	PDGFC	440/12300 =	<u>96.4</u>

1 Results: We observed induction of each of these platelet and coagulation related factors in Rb -/- Jurkat
2 cells following treatment, and to a similar extent as in Rb-sufficient Jurkat cells. Thus, induction of each of
3 these platelet and coagulation related factors - *F12*, *PAFAH2*, *THBS3* and *PDGF-C* - is independent of Rb.

4 Conclusion: In a treatment population dispensed with a class of drugs associated with a reported 5-10%
5 frequency of venous thromboembolism, based on a mechanism of action involving a CDK4/6-R, and in a
6 group of patients who are not routinely screened for Rb status/sufficiency, Rb status, as predicted, is the
7 best indicator of response to CDK4/6 inhibitor treatment (1), whereas expression of aforementioned
8 platelet and coagulation-related factors was independent of Rb. Thus, it had remained unknown whether
9 VTE are dependent or independent of Rb status.

10 However, we have recently discovered and described that CDK6 is activated in human TNBC following
11 deletion of Rb, interestingly, and that the change in CDK6 expression is greater than virtually the change
12 in all genes in the human transcriptome when comparing TNBC primary tumors based on Rb status.

13 We conclude that TNBC patients will likely benefit from treatment with CDK4/6 inhibitors in Rb-sufficient
14 and Rb-deficient states; frequency of venous thrombotic events depending on Rb status in breast cancer
15 (triple negative or otherwise) remained unknown.

16 Citations

17 Asghar, U.S., Kanani, R., Roylance, R. and Mitnacht, S., 2022. Systematic review of molecular
18 biomarkers predictive of resistance to CDK4/6 inhibition in metastatic breast cancer. *JCO Precision
19 Oncology*, 6, p.e2100002.

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21 During our study of gene expression in Rb-sufficient and Rb-deficient triple negative breast cancer
22 in humans, we discovered that the platelet and coagulation-related genes *THSD4* and *TFPI2* were among
23 the genes whose expression was most different when comparing total transcription based on Rb status.

24 We have just described that multiple platelet and coagulation related genes - platelet activating
25 factor *PAFAH2*, thrombospondin *THBS3*, platelet-derived growth factor *PDGF-C* and factor *F12* - were
26 among those whose expression was most different when comparing cultured human cells (Jurkat, a
27 transformed T lymphocyte) before and after in vitro exposure to palbociclib, a CDK4/6 inhibitor.

28 Thus, we asked whether gene expression in the thrombospondin-domain containing gene *THSD4*
and the platelet tissue factor pathway inhibitor *TFPI2* differed in cultured human cells following *in vitro*
exposure to the CDK4/6 inhibitor palbociclib. This analysis was performed using RNA-sequencing;
THSD4 and *TFPI2* was not called (present in the final transcriptome-wide comparison of gene expression
between the two groups in question), but the THSD family member *THSD1* was. *THSD1* induction
following in vitro exposure to palbociclib, unlike *THBS3*, *PAFAH2*, *PDGF-C*, and *F12*, was in fact
dependent on Rb status, as it was significantly decreased in Rb-/- Jurkat as compared to Rb-sufficient
Jurkat.

I. GSE182659

n=3 Jurkat DMSO 72 hours

n=3 Jurkat palbociclib 72 hours

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
55901	3.95e-03	0.3999	-2.882487	-1.15272	29.11	THSD1	4411/12861	65.7

1 II. GSE182659

2 *n*=3 Jurkat Rb^{-/-} DMSO 72 hours

3 *n*=3 Jurkat Rb^{-/-} palbociclib 72 hours

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GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
55901	6.75e-01	0.533	-0.419634	-0.2237457	22.22	THSD1	9715/12300	21.0

6 Citations

7 Levy, G.G., Nichols, W.C., Lian, E.C., Foroud, T., McClintick, J.N., McGee, B.M., Yang, A.Y., Siemieniak, D.R., Stark, K.R., Gruppo, R. and Sarode, R., 2001. Mutations in a member of the ADAMTS gene family cause thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura. *Nature*, 413(6855), pp.488-494.

9 Vadivel, K., Ponnuraj, S.M., Kumar, Y., Zaiss, A.K., Bunce, M.W., Camire, R.M., Wu, L., Evseenko, D., Herschman, H.R., Bajaj, M.S. and Bajaj, S.P., 2014. Platelets contain tissue factor pathway inhibitor-2 derived from megakaryocytes and inhibits fibrinolysis. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 289(45), pp.31647-31661.

12 Elbitar, S., Renard, M., Arnaud, P., Hanna, N., Jacob, M.P., Guo, D.C., Tsutsui, K., Gross, M.S., Kessler, K., Tosolini, L. and Dattilo, V., 2021. Pathogenic variants in THSD4, encoding the ADAMTS-like 6 protein, predispose to inherited thoracic aortic aneurysm. *Genetics in Medicine*, 23(1), pp.111-122.

14 Zheng, X.L., 2013. Structure–function and regulation of ADAMTS-13 protease. *Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis*, 11, pp.11-23.

16 Santos-Martínez, M.J., Medina, C., Jurasz, P. and Radomski, M.W., 2008. Role of metalloproteinases in platelet function. *Thrombosis research*, 121(4), pp.535-542.

18 Li, Z., Nardi, M.A., Li, Y.S., Zhang, W., Pan, R., Dang, S., Yee, H., Quartermain, D., Jonas, S. and Karpatkin, S., 2009. C-terminal ADAMTS-18 fragment induces oxidative platelet fragmentation, dissolves platelet aggregates, and protects against carotid artery occlusion and cerebral stroke. *Blood, The Journal of the American Society of Hematology*, 113(24), pp.6051-6060.

20 Shenkman, B., Budde, U., Angerhaus, D., Lubetsky, A., Savion, N., Seligsohn, U. and Varon, D., 2006. ADAMTS-13 regulates platelet adhesion under flow. *Thrombosis and haemostasis*, 96(08), pp.160-166.

22 CD38, a cell surface glycoprotein that interacts with the platelet-derived cell adhesion molecule CD31, is induced in cultured human cells following *in vitro* exposure to the CDK4/6 inhibitor palbociclib.

24 CD38 possesses function in cell adhesion and was transcriptionally activated at a magnitude greater than the vast majority of genes in the human transcriptome whose expression was measured and compared by RNA-sequencing. Robust induction of CD38 in cultured Jurkat T-lymphocytes was independent of Rb status, as it occurred at a similar magnitude in wild-type and Rb^{-/-} Jurkat cells (transformed human T-lymphocytes).

I. GSE182659

n=3 Jurkat DMSO 72 hours

n=3 Jurkat palbociclib 72 hours

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
952	6.38e-16	0.1243	-8.081798	-1.004561	1202.09	CD38	570/12861	95.6

II. GSE182659

n=3 Jurkat Rb-/- DMSO 72 hours

n=3 Jurkat Rb-/- palbociclib 72 hours

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Symbol	Gene Rank	%DE
952	8.70e-11	0.372	-6.4880267	-2.4105984	760	CD38	36/12300	99.95

Citations

Gallay, N., Anani, L., Lopez, A., Colombat, P., Binet, C., Domenech, J., Weksler, B.B., Malavasi, F. and Herault, O., 2007. The Role of Platelet/Endothelial Cell Adhesion Molecule-1 (CD31) and CD38 Antigens in Marrow Microenvironmental Retention of Acute Myelogenous Leukemia Cells. *Cancer research*, 67(18), pp.8624-8632.

Mehta, K., Shahid, U. and Malavasi, F., 1996. Human CD38, a cell-surface protein with multiple functions. *The FASEB Journal*, 10(12), pp.1408-1417.

Zucchetto, A., Vaisitti, T., Benedetti, D., Tissino, E., Bertagnolo, V., Rossi, D., Bomben, R., Dal Bo, M., Del Principe, M.I., Gorgone, A. and Pozzato, G., 2012. The CD49d/CD29 complex is physically and functionally associated with CD38 in B-cell chronic lymphocytic leukemia cells. *Leukemia*, 26(6), pp.1301-1312.

Magnone, M., Basile, G., Bruzzese, D., Guida, L., Signorello, M.G., Chothi, M.P., Bruzzone, S., Millo, E., Qi, A.D., Nicholas, R.A. and Kassack, M.U., 2008. Adenylic dinucleotides produced by CD38 are negative endogenous modulators of platelet aggregation. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 283(36), pp.24460-24468.

After profiling whole transcriptome gene expression changes in multiple *in vitro* systems, in epithelial and hematopoietic cell types following exposure to CDK4/6 inhibitors, we utilized a second whole transcriptome technology known as co-expression analysis to search for genes that contribute to VTE in humans treated with CDK4/6 inhibitors. We queried the whole transcriptome of multiple tissue settings, searching only in megakaryocytes, to identify genes co-regulated by the cyclin-dependent kinases CDK4 and CDK6 in platelets since the cell of origin for CDK4/6-related DVT has not yet been described but is most likely to originate from the platelet. We identified three integrin or integrin-related genes as putative contributors to this pharmacologically-associated phenotype.

1 CDK4/CDK6 co-regulated integrin genes in platelets.

2 I. The very late antigen VLA-4 is a heterodimer composed of CD49d (alpha 4) and CD29 (beta 1).
3 The integrin itga4 (CD49d) was a top CDK4/6 co-regulated gene in platelets.

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<u>Rank</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Coexpression Score</u>	<u>p-value</u>
497	ITGA4	0.9556	0.0175

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6 % transcriptome-wide co-expression: 497/17972=97.2

7 VLA heterodimers have been described to exist on the surface of platelets (1) and VLA-4 activation
8 is described to accelerate pro-platelet formation (2).

9 Citations

10 Matsunaga, T., Fukai, F., Kameda, T., Shide, K., Shimoda, H., Torii, E., Kamiunten, A., Sekine, M.,
11 Yamamoto, S., Hidaka, T. and Kubuki, Y., 2012. Potentiated activation of VLA-4 and VLA-5 accelerates
12 proplatelet-like formation. *Annals of hematology*, 91, pp.1633-1643.

13 Hemler, M.E., Crouse, C., Takada, Y. and Sonnenberg, A., 1988. Multiple very late antigen (VLA)
14 heterodimers on platelets. Evidence for distinct VLA-2, VLA-5 (fibronectin receptor), and VLA-6 structures.
15 *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 263(16), pp.7660-7665.

16 II. Cell adhesion molecule ICAM4

17 Cell adhesion molecule ICAM4 was a top CDK4/6 co-regulated gene when considering all genes
18 expressed in the megakaryocyte transcriptome.

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<u>Rank</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Coexpression Score</u>	<u>p-value</u>
1574	ICAM4	0.7022	0.0116

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21 Description: intercellular adhesion molecule 4 (Landsteiner-Wiener blood group)

22 % transcriptome-wide co-expression: 1574/17972=91.2

23 ICAM4 was described as a receptor for the platelet fibrinogen receptor, GPIIb/IIIa. GPIIb/IIIa (CD41/CD61)
24 is one of a small group of platelet integrins central to platelet aggregation/thrombosis.

25 III. Itgb3bp

26 Finally, we discovered a third integrin or integrin-associated molecule, Itgb3bp, also known as
27 beta3-endonexin, as a CDK4/6 co-regulated gene in megakaryocytes. Itgb3bp expression has been
28 described as important for GPIIb/IIIa activation in some contexts and was identified as a top dys-regulated
gene in a patient with impaired platelet aggregation; beta3-endonexin can modulate affinity for the platelet
integrin GPIIb/IIIa through the cytoplasmic tail of integrin beta3.

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<u>Rank</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Co-expression Score</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>Description</u>
156	ITGB3BP	1.1422	0.0213	integrin beta 3 binding protein (beta3-endonexin)

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31 Rank: 156/17972=99.1

[Of note, none of the classically understood platelet integrin binding partners osteopontin (*Spp1*) vitronectin, laminin, fibronectin, or fibrinogen were transcriptionally co-regulated with CDK4/6]

Citations

Sun, L., Gorospe, J.R., Hoffman, E.P. and Rao, A.K., 2007. Decreased platelet expression of myosin regulatory light chain polypeptide (MYL9) and other genes with platelet dysfunction and CBFA2/RUNX1 mutation: insights from platelet expression profiling. *Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis*, 5(1), pp.146-154.

Caparros-Perez, E., Teruel-Montoya, R., López-Andreo, M.J., Llanos, M.C., Rivera, J., Palma-Barqueros, V., Blanco, J.E., Vicente, V., Martínez, C. and Ferrer-Marín, F., 2017. Comprehensive comparison of neonate and adult human platelet transcriptomes. *PLoS One*, 12(8), p.e0183042.

Kashiwagi, H., Schwartz, M.A., Eigenthaler, M., Davis, K.A., Ginsberg, M.H. and Shattil, S.J., 1997. Affinity modulation of platelet integrin $\alpha\text{IIb}\beta\text{3}$ by β3 -endonexin, a selective binding partner of the β3 integrin cytoplasmic tail. *The Journal of cell biology*, 137(6), pp.1433-1443.

Finally, we examined a final cellular context in which to understand the effect of CDK4/6 inhibition on expression of genes important for clotting. We studied total transcription in the primary tumors of women with triple negative breast cancer (TNBC); we compared gene expression between tumors that were Rb sufficient and Rb deficient. We surmised that CDK4/6 inhibition would mimic Rb sufficiency and that examining transcripts whose expression was most de-regulated by genetic Rb sufficiency that mimicked Rb sufficiency resulting from pharmacologic CDK4/6 inhibition would inform efforts to understand suggested increase in DVT risk from the -ciclib family of CDK4/6 inhibitors. .

GSE108757

n=3 TNBC; human; RB deficient

n=3 TNBC; human; RB sufficient

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
79875	3.16e-23	0.437	-9.927546	-4.3403132	524.77	THSD4	15/16255	99.9
7980	3.31e-16	0.916	-8.1616	-7.4722775	252.36	TFPI2	28/16255	99.8
2151	1.15e-08	0.602	-5.706791	-3.4365941	82.44	F2RL2	113/16255	99.3
5051	1.28e-01	0.524	-1.521693	-0.7976472	105.36	PAFAH2	4621/16255	71.6

Indeed, the expression of the tissue factor pathway inhibitor TFPI2, the thrombospondin type 1 domain containing 4 THSD4, and coagulation factor II thrombin receptor-like 2 *F2RL2* was augmented significantly by genetic Rb sufficiency which simulated CDK4/6 pharmacologic inhibition resulting in Rb sufficiency.

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Discussion

The difference in DVT rate between patients with breast cancer at baseline, patients receiving endocrine therapy, and patients receiving CDK4/6 inhibitors in conjunction with ET agents like tamoxifen requires clear delineation to understand the true magnitude of DVT risk in patients receiving CDK4/6 inhibitor therapy. We described here a multifactorial molecular mechanism which appears to suggest an intrinsic link between Rb-dependent tumor suppression and the clotting cascade.

1 **References**

2 1. Mamoor, S. 2024. Use of a novel dual chemotherapy, a PARP1 inhibitor in conjunction with a
3 CDK4/6 inhibitor, for treatment of solid tumors of the breast and lungs in humans.
4 2. Mamoor, S. 2024. CDK4 is activated in lung metastasis in human breast cancer.
5 3. Mamoor, S. 2024. CDK4 is activated in central nervous system metastasis in human breast
6 cancer.
7 4. Mamoor, S. 2024. CDK4/6 inhibition with -ciclids (palbociclib, ribociclib, and abemaciclib)
8 antagonizes Xist-associated interleukin enhancer factor ILF3 activation in hormone positive (HR+) breast
9 cancer resulting from endocrine therapy.
10 5. Mamoor, S. 2024. Xist modulates semaphorin expression in solid tumors altering CNS outcomes,
11 and pharmacological CDK4/6 inhibition antagonizes this function.
12 6. Mahajan, A., Brunson, A., Adesina, O., Keegan, T.H. and Wun, T., 2022. The incidence of
13 cancer-associated thrombosis is increasing over time. *Blood advances*, 6(1), pp.307-320.
14 7. Decensi, A., Maisonneuve, P., Rotmensz, N., Bettega, D., Costa, A., Sacchini, V., Salvioni, A.,
15 Travaglini, R., Oliviero, P., D'Aiuto, G. and Gulisano, M., 2005. Effect of tamoxifen on venous
16 thromboembolic events in a breast cancer prevention trial. *Circulation*, 111(5), pp.650-656.
17 8. Olson, S.R., DeLoughery, T.G. and Shatzel, J.J., 2019. Cyclin-dependent kinase
18 inhibitor-associated thromboembolism. *JAMA oncology*, 5(2), pp.141-142.
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